

Research Paper

Rapid microwave-assisted hydrothermal in situ synthesis of nano-ZnS/kaolinite nanocomposite: A non-toxic photocatalyst active under UV and sunlight

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ABSTRACT

Clay mineral kaolinite (K) is suitable for the immobilization of nano-ZnS leading to increase in its photocatalytic activity (PA). Two synthesis methods, conventional hydrothermal (H) and microwave-assisted hydrothermal (M), and various reaction parameters (six reaction times, three $n_{\text{Zn}}:n_{\text{S}}$ molar ratios) for nano-ZnS/K nanocomposites were compared. In addition to XRPD, FTIR, DRS and SEM analyses, PA was determined on acid orange 7 under UV irradiation ($\lambda = 365$ nm), and for selected samples also under natural sunlight. After 360 min of UV irradiation, PA 98 % (H; 210 min; 1:1) and 90 % (M; 30 min; 1:1) were reached. Under the sunlight, PA 97 % (H; 210 min; 2:1) and 93 % (M; 20 min; 2:1) were achieved after 540 min, respectively. Lipid peroxidation tests revealed the inhibition of peroxidation for all nanocomposites. The non-toxicity and high PA under sunlight suggest the potential for outdoor use of nanocomposites in water purification or construction industry.

1. Introduction

Nanostructured zinc sulfide (nano-ZnS), a photocatalyst having wide direct band gap energy ($E_g \approx 3.7$ eV) and rapidly forming holes as well as photoexcited electrons with strongly negative reduction potential, exhibits good ability to degrade organic pollutants or greenhouse gases, interesting optical properties, or antibacterial effects (Table 1). The nanoscale of ZnS favorable for photocatalysis also has its drawback, as free nano-ZnS is prone to agglomeration reducing photocatalytic efficiency (Bhuvanewari et al., 2018; Chen and Yu, 2013; Ebrahimi et al., 2017a; Kabilaphat et al., 2015). To avoid this, various support matrices are used, and the matrix together with nano-ZnS forms a functional material – a nanocomposite. In studies focused on ZnS-based nanocomposites, the matrices are e.g. organic macromolecular substances whose low wear resistance and thermal stability are increased by the

ZnS addition (Wang et al., 2014; Yang et al., 2023), layered double hydroxides often requiring very time-consuming synthesis ranging from 12 to 77 h, although a faster mechanochemical synthesis lasting 2 h has also been reported (Table 1), or graphene/(reduced) graphene oxide, the synthesis of which is also not easy and time consuming (Table 1), and its use in practical applications is still quite limited (Hu et al., 2023).

Suitable matrices for ZnS immobilization are readily available and cheap, chemically stable and non-toxic natural clay minerals. Montmorillonite significantly dominates (Table 1), but halloysite and bentonite were also reported (Table 1), as well as synthetic magadiite (synthesis duration 96 h (Table 1)). Some authors organophilized clay minerals prior to use (Ghiaci et al., 2009; Miao et al., 2006).

Nano-ZnS used in nanocomposites is synthesized by precipitation, hydrothermal/solvothermal (mostly in autoclave), or mechanochemical method from various zinc and sulfur precursors, sometimes also with the

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use of stabilizing agent (Table 1). Nanocomposites are prepared either by mixing the pre-synthesized nano-ZnS with a matrix, or by in situ synthesis of nano-ZnS on a matrix, less often by synthesis of matrix on nano-ZnS or joint synthesis of nano-ZnS and matrix (Table 1).

A common feature of the vast majority of ZnS-containing nanocomposites is a long preparation time (up to 48 h; Table 1), even longer if pre-synthesis of components is required and taken into account (up to 77 h; Table 1). A total preparation time of less than 5 h is not commonly used for these nanocomposites (Table 1), although the short preparation time is an important prerequisite for production and use in practice. While the rapid synthesis (lasting tens of seconds or minutes) of pure nano-ZnS or nano-ZnS/graphene (or graphene oxide) nanocomposites using a microwave-assisted hydrothermal method has already been reported (Table 1), to the best of our knowledge this approach has not yet been used for the preparation of nanocomposites containing nano-ZnS and clay mineral matrix.

This work is therefore focused on the rapid microwave-assisted hydrothermal in situ synthesis of nano-ZnS on matrix and its comparison with conventional hydrothermal in situ synthesis. An autoclave was not used and the synthesis was carried out under atmospheric pressure at a

temperature of 100 °C. With regard to the simplicity of preparation and time saving, a natural clay mineral was chosen as the matrix. Our research group dealing with the preparation of clay-based nanocomposites has previously demonstrated that the clay mineral kaolinite is suitable for the immobilization of nanophotocatalysts, either TiO₂ (Mamulová Kutláková et al., 2011; Tokarcíková et al., 2014) or ZnO (Janíková et al., 2017; Mamulová Kutláková et al., 2015), and ZnS is thus next in the series. Other authors also reported the use of kaolinite as a component of various nanocomposites (Gashti and Almasian, 2012; Nallis et al., 2013; Morjène et al., 2021; de Oliveira et al., 2023).

The aim of this work is to investigate the influence of the preparation method (microwave-assisted vs. conventional hydrothermal in situ synthesis) and reaction conditions (three different reaction times for each preparation method and three molar ratios $n_{Zn}:n_S$ for each reaction time) on the morphology and photocatalytic properties of nano-ZnS on kaolinite. Nanocomposites were studied using X-ray diffraction analysis, scanning electron microscopy, and infrared, Raman, photoluminescence and UV-VIS diffuse reflectance spectroscopy. Photocatalytic activity (PA) was determined by degradation of the acid orange 7, an acidic azo dye containing the -N=N- chromophore. Acid orange 7 is commonly

Table 1

Various applications of ZnS-based materials, matrices used, synthesis methods (microwave-assisted methods marked with MW), precursors of zinc (Zn_{prec}) and sulfur (S_{prec}) including capping agents (cap) are provided. Reaction times for matrix synthesis (t_m , in h), for ZnS synthesis (t_{ZnS} , in h), and for the synthesis of complete ZnS-based material ($t_{ZnS/m}$) are listed including References.

Application	Matrix	Synthesis	Zn_{prec}	S_{prec}	cap	t_m	t_{ZnS}	$t_{ZnS/m}$	Ref.
PA(AR)	LDH	HT(100 °C) ^{1,3}	Zn(Ac) ₂	Na ₂ S	–	48	3	24 h	Amani-Ghadim et al. (2019)
PA(H ₂ O)*	LDH	HTac(160 °C) ²	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	Na ₂ S	–	24	1	24 h	Gao et al. (2021)
PA(TC)	LDH	HTac(180 °C) ²	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	THU	–	–	–	12 h	Hu et al. (2021)
PA(CR)	LDH	PR ²	ZnCl ₂	Na ₂ S	–	48	–	24 h	Intachai et al. (2023)
PA(MB)	LDH	PR ¹	ZnCl ₂	Na ₂ S	–	14	NP	5 h	Bhuvaneswari et al. (2018)
PA(CH ₃ OH)*	LDH	ST(100 °C) ²	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	THU	–	77	–	5 h	Gil et al. (2020)
PA(RhB)	LDH	MCH ⁴	comp. ^b	Na ₂ S	–	2	–	2 h	Li et al. (2017)
PA(NPh)	rGO	STac(170 °C) ²	Zn(Ac) ₂	THU	–	27	–	30 h	Ibrahim et al. (2017)
OP	G	HTac(180 °C) ²	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	CS ₂	–	–	–	13 h	Pan and Liu (2012)
PA(RR)	LDH + GO	PR ⁴	Zn(Ac) ₂	Na ₂ S	–	–	–	24 h	Seyed Dorraji et al. (2019)
OP	MMT	PR ²	ZnCl ₂	Na ₂ S	CTB	–	24 [‡]	24 h	Kabilaphat et al. (2015)
PA(CO ₂)	MMT	PR ¹	Zn(Ac) ₂	Na ₂ S	CTB	–	1	24 h	Ebrahimi et al. (2017a)
PA(CO ₂)	MMT	PR ¹	ZnCl ₂	Na ₂ S	CTB	–	1	24 h	Ebrahimi et al. (2017b)
PA(CO ₂)	MMT	PR ¹	Zn(Ac) ₂	Na ₂ S	CTB	–	NP	24 h	Kočí et al. (2014, 2017)
PA(CO ₂)	MMT	PR ¹	Zn(Ac) ₂	Na ₂ S	CTB	–	NP	24 h	Kozák et al. (2010)
PA(CO ₂)	MMT	PR ¹	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	Na ₂ S	CTB	–	NP	24 h	Kozák et al. (2010)
PA(CO ₂)	MMT	PR ¹	ZnSO ₄	Na ₂ S	CTB	–	NP	24 h	Kozák et al. (2010)
PA(N ₂ O)	MMT	PR ¹	Zn(Ac) ₂	Na ₂ S	CTB	–	NP	24 h	Obalová et al. (2014)
PA(Phe)	MMT	PR ¹	Zn(Ac) ₂	Na ₂ S	CTB	–	NP	24 h	Praus et al. (2012)
PA(CO ₂)	MMT	PR ¹	Zn(Ac) ₂	Na ₂ S	CTB	–	NP	24 h	Praus et al. (2013)
OP	MMT	MCH ²	ZnCl ₂	Na ₂ S	–	–	–	24 h	Khaorapapong et al. (2010)
PA(EoB)	MMT	HTac(170 °C) ²	Zn(Ac) ₂	THU	–	–	–	4 h	Miao et al. (2006)
PA(EoB)	BEN	PR ²	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	Na ₂ S	–	–	–	24 h	Ghiaci et al. (2009)
PA(EoB)	HAL	PR ¹	Zn(Ac) ₂	TAA	–	–	–	24 h	Zhang and Yang (2013)
ADS(Al ³⁺)	HAL	HTac(180 °C) ¹	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	THU	–	–	–	12 h	Yuan et al. (2022)
AB	–	PR	ZnCl ₂	Na ₂ S	–	–	–	12 h	Vijayan et al. (2021)
OP	MAG	PR	comp. ^a	Na ₂ S	–	96	72 [‡]	NP	Chen and Yu (2013)
TT	NSI	HTac(170 °C) ¹	Zn(Ac) ₂	THU	–	8	–	4 h	Yang et al. (2023)
PA(MB)	GO	HT-MW ²	Zn(Ac) ₂	TAA	–	7.5	–	20 min	Hu et al. (2011)
PA(MO)	G	ST-MW ¹	ZnCl ₂	TAA	PVP	–	–	20 min	Zeng et al. (2018)
OP	GO	ST-MW ²	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	S	–	2.5	–	15 min	Bai et al. (2013)
OP	–	ST-MW	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	THU	–	–	–	6 min	La Porta et al. (2013)
OP	–	ST-MW	Zn(Ac) ₂	THU	–	–	–	6 min	La Porta et al. (2013)
OP	–	ST-MW	ZnCl ₂	THU	–	–	–	6 min	La Porta et al. (2013)
PA(MB)	–	PR-MW	ZnCl ₂	TAA	PVP	–	–	5 min	Soltani et al. (2014)
OP	–	PR-MW	Zn(Ac) ₂	TAA	IL	–	–	1–2 min	Goharshadi et al. (2013)
PA(MB)	rGO	PR-MW ¹	Zn(Ac) ₂	Na ₂ S	–	≥1 [†]	–	20 s	Thangavel et al. (2016)
PA(RhB)	rGO	PR-MW ¹	Zn(Ac) ₂	Na ₂ S	–	≥1 [†]	–	20 s	Thangavel et al. (2016)

Application: PA – photocatalytic activity (AR – acid red 14, CR – congo red, EoB – Eosin B, MB – methylene blue, MO – methylene orange, NPh – 4-nitrophenol, Phe – phenol, RhB – rhodamine B, RR – reactive red 43, TC – tetracycline, * – H₂ production), OP – optical properties, AB – antibacterial effect, TT – tribology and thermostability, ADS – adsorption; matrix: BEN – bentonite, G – graphene, GO – graphene oxide, rGO – reduced graphene oxide, HAL – halloysite, LDH – layered double hydroxide, MAG – magadiite, MMT – montmorillonite, NSI – nanosilica; synthesis: HT – hydrothermal, ST – solvothermal, PR – precipitation, MCH – mechano-chemical, ac – autoclave, 1 – pre-synthesis of ZnS, 2 – in situ synthesis of ZnS on matrix, 3 – in situ synthesis of matrix on ZnS, 4 – joint synthesis of matrix and ZnS; Zn_{prec} : Zn(Ac)₂ – zinc acetate, comp.^a – Zn(NH₃)₄²⁺, comp.^b – Zn₄CO₃(OH)₆·H₂O; S_{prec} : S – powdered sulfur, TAA – thioacetamide, THU – thiourea; cap: CTB – cetrimonium bromide, PVP – polyvinylpyrrolidone; t_m : † – estimated from the description in Hummers and Offeman (1958); t_{ZnS} : ‡ – intercalation of Zn precursor only.

used as a model dye to test the PA of photocatalysts (Mamulová Kutláková et al., 2015; Ouni et al., 2022; Rusek et al., 2022). In practice, it is used e.g. in the textile industry, and its concentration in wastewater reaches up to 50 mg/L (Ong et al., 2005; Dutta et al., 2024). PA tests in our work were performed under UV radiation and, for selected samples, also under natural sunlight. Potential toxicity of nano-ZnS/kaolinite nanocomposites was evaluated by lipid peroxidation tests. Amount of malondialdehyde, one of the final products of polyunsaturated fatty acids peroxidation in cells (and oxidative stress marker associated with development of cancer (Akbulut et al., 2003)), has been used as an indicator of the toxicity of nanocomposites.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Zinc chloride (ZnCl₂; anhydrous p.a.) from Lach-Ner s.r.o., Czech Republic, and sodium sulfide (Na₂S; anhydrous granulated) from Alfa Aesar, Thermo Fisher Scientific s.r.o., Czech Republic, were used without any further purification. Kaolin KKAF, clay containing mainly kaolinite (K), a phyllosilicate of 1:1 type with ideal crystallochemical formula Al₄Si₄O₁₀(OH)₈, was purchased from LB Minerals, s.r.o., Czech Republic. According to the previously reported chemical composition (Janíková et al., 2017), the KKAF contains ~82 mass% of K, ~10 mass% of muscovite, and ~8 mass% of quartz (Table A1). As received in powder form, the kaolin was sieved and size fraction <40 μm was used. Acid orange 7 (C₁₀H₆(OH)N=N(C₆H₄)SO₃⁻Na⁺) was obtained from Synthesia a.s. (Czech Republic). From following compounds were used for lipid peroxidation test. Sodium dihydrogen phosphate dihydrate (NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O; g.r.), disodium hydrogen phosphate dodecahydrate (Na₂HPO₄·12H₂O; g.r.), and trichloroacetic acid (C₂HCl₃O₂; g.r.) were purchased from Lach-Ner s.r.o., Czech Republic. Hydrochloric acid (HCl; 35 %, a.g.) and n-butanol (C₄H₁₀O; a.g.) were purchased from Penta chemicals s.r.o., Czech Republic. Thiobarbituric acid (C₄H₄N₂O₂S; g.r.) and butylhydroxytoluene (C₁₅H₂₄O; food grade) were purchased from PanReac AppliChem, IWT Reagents s.r.o., Czech Republic. Linoleic acid (C₁₈H₃₂O₂; ≥99 %) and ethanol (C₂H₆O; 96 %) were purchased from VWR International, LLC, Czech Republic.

2.2. Synthesis of nanocomposites

Aqueous solutions (1, 1.5, 2 M) of ZnCl₂ and 1 M solution of Na₂S (i.e. molar ratios of ZnS precursors $n_{Zn}:n_S$ were 1:1, 1.5:1, 2:1) were mixed with water suspension of K (ZnS precursors : K mass ratio was 1:1 for all samples). These reaction solutions were heated at 100 °C by magnetic stirrer (Heidolph, MR Hei-Standard) or microwave oven (SENCOR SMW 2717). In the conventional hydrothermal synthesis, the reaction solutions were heated and stirred for 90, 150, and 210 min. In the microwave-assisted hydrothermal synthesis, microwave oven was operating at 462 W for 10, 20, and 30 min. White nano-ZnS/K precipitates were washed two times with distilled water, separated by centrifugation (10 min, 6000 rpm, Hettich ZENTRIFUGEN, Rotina 420) and dried at 100 °C (UNE 300, Memmert) overnight. A scheme of the procedure is provided in Fig. A1. Finally, the samples were calcined in muffle oven (LMH 11/12, LAC) with a temperature rise 4.6 °C/min at 300 °C and 1 h holding time.

Samples obtained using conventional hydrothermal (H) and microwave-assisted hydrothermal (M) synthesis were denoted as cHt_{ZnS} and cMt_{ZnS}, respectively, where *c* represents ZnCl₂ molar concentration (i.e. 1, 1.5, or 2 M), *t*_{ZnS} represents time (i.e. 90, 150, 210 min for H and 10, 20, 30 min for M synthesis).

2.3. Characterization of nanocomposites

X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) patterns were recorded (in the range of 5–100° 2θ) in reflection mode and symmetrical Bragg-Brentano

arrangement by Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer equipped with fast position sensitive detector VÅNTEC 1 and Co lamp ($\lambda(\text{Co}_{K\alpha}) = 0.1789$ nm; $U = 35$ kV; $I = 25$ mA). Scanning speed and increment were $0.8^\circ \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and 0.03° , respectively. Phase composition was determined using ICDD PDF-2 Release 2020 database. ZnS crystallite sizes (L_c) were calculated from (111) reflection by Scherrer equation (Scherrer, 1918):

$$L_c = \lambda \cdot K / (\beta \cdot \cos \theta) \quad (1)$$

where λ is the Co_{Kα} wavelength (0.1789 nm), K is a dimensionless shape factor (0.89) used for approximately spherical particle regardless of their actual dimensions (Monshi et al., 2012), β is full width at half maximum of the ZnS(111) reflection (°), and θ is a position of the reflection (°).

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded by Nicolet 6700 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) with diamond ATR crystal (in a range of wavenumbers of 400–4000 cm⁻¹, spectral resolution 4 cm⁻¹, 32 scans).

Morphology and elemental composition were studied using scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL JSM-7610Fplus (Jeol Ltd., Japan) equipped with energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS). Samples were placed on carbon tape on the target and sputtered by Pt (layer thickness ~20 nm) using Q150V ES plus (Quorum Technologies Ltd., UK) coater. To take the SEM micrographs, accelerating voltage of 10 kV was used. Particle sizes were determined from the micrographs using GWYDDION software (Nečas and Klapetek, 2012).

Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) was used to measure all powder samples for three series. DRS spectra were measured by Shimadzu UV-2600 Series instrument in the wavelength range of 250–800 nm. An external 2D detector was used. As a reference sample was used BaSO₄. The average diameter of the integrating sphere type ISR-2600 was 60 mm. Reflectance spectra was recorded as a function of wavelength. Tauc curves were obtained using the Kubelka-Munk (*K-M*) function (Kubelka and Munk, 1931), which depends on the forbidden bandgap energy values (E_g in eV) of individual nanocomposites:

$$F(R) = (1-R)^r / (2R) \quad (2)$$

where R is a reflectance obtained from the DRS spectrum, and $r = 2$. Tauc plot (Tauc et al., 1966) was obtained by reflectance transformation according to the *K-M* function via the equation:

$$h \cdot \nu / F(R) h \cdot \nu = A \cdot (h \cdot \nu - E_g)^2 \quad (3)$$

where $h \cdot \nu$ and A is photon energy (eV) and absorption constant, respectively. Direct E_g values were obtained from extrapolation of the linear region of curve depending $(F(R)h \cdot \nu)^{1/2}$ vs. $h \cdot \nu$ onto the horizontal axis.

2.4. Photocatalytic experiments

Photocatalytic activity (PA) was evaluated by photodegradation of acid orange 7 azo dye (AO7; $M = 350.32$ g/mol) under UV irradiation ($\lambda = 365$ nm) using UVP Pen-ray lamp. 50 mg of nanocomposite was added to 70 mL of AO7 aqueous solution ($c = 4.4707 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol/L; $m_{AO7} \approx 1$ mg in the solution) and stirred for 1 h in the dark to reach the adsorption equilibrium. Then it was exposed to UV irradiation for 360 min. Uncalcined samples exhibiting the highest PA under UV were also tested under natural sunlight (SL). Duration of the test and the daily amount of SL was 540 min and 20 MJ/m², respectively. Photolysis, i.e. degradation of pure AO7 under UV irradiation and SL, was also tested.

The suspension after UV or SL irradiation was filtered through a ProFill syringe filter (hydrophilic, regenerated cellulose, diameter 30 mm, pore size 0.45 μm) into a cuvette. Discoloration of AO7 filtrated solution was evaluated using UV-VIS spectrometer (CINTRA 303 UV-VIS, quartz glass cuvette 10 mm) according to the equation:

$$\text{PA (\%)} = (1 - (A_t/A_0)) \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

where A_t and A_0 are intensities of AO7 absorption maximum (480

nm) for suspension irradiated for time t and suspension before irradiation, respectively. Two beams were used, one passing through the AO7 aqueous solution and one passing through the blank reference (distilled water).

Half-life time of AO7 ($\tau_{1/2}$) was calculated according to the equation:

$$\tau_{1/2} = \ln(2)/k_{AO7} \quad (5)$$

where k_{AO7} is the rate constant of the photocatalytic reaction (Badr et al., 2008).

2.5. Lipid peroxidation testing

These in vitro tests, performed in triplicate on linoleic acid (one of the cell membrane fatty acids), were used for a basic investigation of the potential toxicity of the samples. Nano-TiO₂ (average particle size of ~21 nm) with known toxic effects on the organisms was used as a positive control (Corazzi et al., 2014; Rajhelová et al., 2019). Each sample and positive control (10 mg) were put into conical shaped plastic tubes. Then 3 mL of buffered (0.01 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.4) micellar dispersion of linoleic acid (0.001 M) containing 2.5 mass% ethanol were added into the tubes. A buffered dispersion of linoleic acid without sample was used as a negative control. The tubes were capped, mixed for ~10 s (IKA VORTEX GENIUS 3) and incubated (NB-205, N-BIOTEX) for 72 h with continuous mixing (200 rpm) while exposed to the UV illumination (ReptiGlo 5.0 Compact bulb, 26 W). After incubation, 0.1 mL of butylhydroxytoluene (0.2 mass%) were used for stopping the reaction. 1.5 mL of each solution was centrifuged for 30 min at 12000 rpm (MIKRO 120, Hettich Zentrifugen) to obtain supernatant solution. Thiobarbituric acid (TBA; 0.034 M) was dissolved in a mixture of HCl (0.25 M) and trichloroacetic acid (0.92 M). The resulting TBA solution (2 mL) was added into 1 mL of the supernatant solution and incubated in a boiling water bath ~100 °C for 30 min (IKA C-MAG HS7 thermostatic mixer, IKA ETS-D5 digital thermometer) to obtain pink chromogen, indicating reaction of the malondialdehyde (MDA) with TBA. The cooled solutions were mixed with 1-butanol (3 mL) to extract the pink chromogen (MDA-TBA) into the organic phase. Amount of MDA produced during incubation was determined spectrophotometrically (CINTRA 303 UV-VIS, quartz glass cuvette 10 mm) from absorbance of the pink MDA-TBA complex (532 nm), a reliable estimator of lipid peroxidation (Janero, 1990; Rajhelová et al., 2019). Two beams were used, one passing through the sample (MDA-TBA in 1-butanol) and one passing through the blank reference (1-butanol).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structure of nanocomposites

Significant reflection (111), (220), and (311) confirmed presence of sphalerite, cubic phase (PDF No. 005-0566), in all samples of nano-

ZnS nanocomposites (see Fig. 1). The most frequent reflections including the dominant one correspond to kaolinite (K; PDF No. 58-2028). To save space, the full intensities of the K(001) reflections are not shown in the Fig. 1. The reader is referred to the original data (see the Data Availability). Muscovite (M; PDF No. 58-2037) and quartz (Q; PDF No. 46-1045), common admixtures of natural clay minerals, are also present in all samples. The ZnS(111) reflection were used to calculate crystallite sizes (L_c) provided in section 3.2. *Photocatalytic activity of nanocomposites.*

FTIR spectra of the nano-ZnS/K nanocomposites (Fig. 2) show approximately the same positions of characteristic bands. Characteristic bands of Zn-S bonds are connected to asymmetric stretching vibration at positions 1114 and 828 cm⁻¹. Bands at 641 and 643 cm⁻¹ (H and M synthesis) correspond to Zn-S stretching vibrations. Bands at 603 and 605 cm⁻¹ (H and M synthesis) belong to Zn-S symmetric stretching vibration (Hwang et al., 2016). Each FTIR spectrum contains characteristic bands of K overlapping some characteristic Zn-S bands. Significant bands corresponding to the inner and outer octahedral structure of Al-OH stretching (3690-3619 cm⁻¹) and Al-OH deformation (935-937, and 911 cm⁻¹) vibrations, Si-O bonds (1114, 788, 460-461, and 418-421 cm⁻¹), Si-O-Al stretching and deformation vibrations (1004, 751, 687-689, and 529 cm⁻¹) and Si-O-Si stretching vibration (1028 cm⁻¹) (Madejova, 2001; Van der Marel, 1976) can be found in all spectra. Since the four OH vibration bands (3690-3619 cm⁻¹) are not noticeable in Figs. 2a,b, the reader is referred to the detail of the spectra in Fig. A2. Bands at 3384/3421 and 1637 cm⁻¹ (stretching and deformation OH- vibrations, respectively) with low intensity indicate the presence of air moisture (Jha et al., 2013).

3.2. Photocatalytic activity of nanocomposites

The PA was evaluated on the calcined and uncalcined samples after 360 min of UV irradiation (Fig. 3). Comparison with photolysis and pure K sample clearly confirms the PA of nano-ZnS/K. The discoloration of the AO7 aqueous solution shows the ability of nano-ZnS/K to break the N=N bond in AO7 molecules (Cardito et al., 2024). The slightly higher value of PA for K compared to photolysis (10 % vs. 4 %, respectively, after 360 min; Table 2) can be explained by the weak attraction of AO7 and K. None of the components of KKAF (Fig. 1) is photoactive, but the OH groups on the edges of kaolinite or muscovite can weakly interact with the OH group of AO7.

After 360 min of UV irradiation, H synthesized nano-ZnS/K samples before calcination (Fig. 3a) had the PA 62-80 %, while the calcination lead to increase in PA to 86-98 %. The increased PA with increasing molar ratio can be seen in uncalcined samples, however it is not observed in the calcined samples. For the calcined samples, the molar ratio of the ZnS precursors does not have influence on the PA. The increasing reaction time slightly increased the PA: 89, 90, 96 % in average for reaction time 90, 150, 210 min, respectively. The 1H210

Fig. 1. XRPD patterns of the nanocomposites nano-ZnS/K prepared by (a) H synthesis and (b) M synthesis. K, M and Q is the designation for kaolinite, muscovite and quartz, respectively.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of the nanocomposite nano-ZnS/K prepared by (a) H synthesis and (b) M synthesis.

Fig. 3. The PA values after 360 min of UV irradiation ($\lambda = 365$ nm) of the nano-ZnS/K uncalcined (hatched) and calcined (filled with colour) samples prepared by (a) H synthesis and (b) M synthesis in comparison with photolysis (P) and pure K instead of nano-ZnS/K. Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetic plots of the nano-ZnS/K samples prepared by (c) H synthesis and (d) M synthesis. For the amount of carbon in solution after PA experiments, see Table A2.

sample, i.e. the sample synthesized using the longest reaction time and 1:1 molar ratio, had the highest PA (98 %).

Uncalcined M synthesized nano-ZnS/K samples had the PA values 60–75 %, calcination led to increase in the PA (58–90 %) in average (Fig. 3b). However, there was a slight decrease in PA for the samples 1M20, 1.5M20, 2M20, and 2M30 compared to same samples before calcination. The average PA = 80, 62, 79 % for reaction time 10, 20, 30 min, respectively, show that the reaction time > 10 min is not necessary to achieve the higher PA. Increasing the molar ratio led to an increase in PA only for a reaction time of 20 min (Fig. 3b). Samples 1M30 and 1.5M10 exhibit the highest PA (90 % and 86 %, respectively). H synthesis led to more uniform PA values than M synthesis (compare Figs. 3a and b).

The Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetic plots of H synthesized nano-ZnS/

K samples (Fig. 3c) confirm the positive effect of the longest reaction time (210 min) on the PA, but positive effect of the highest molar ratio was not observed. Even the sample 1H210 having the lowest PA (49 %) after 120 min of UV irradiation reached the highest PA (98 %) of all samples after 360 min. M synthesized nano-ZnS/K samples reaction time does not have a significant effect on PA after 360 min. However, samples 1M10 and 1.5M10 reached PA < 50 % already after 120 min of UV irradiation (Fig. 3d).

The PA values after 120 and 360 min of UV irradiation, reaction rate constant (k_{AO7}), half-life time of AO7 ($\tau_{1/2}$), E_g , and L_C for all nano-ZnS/K samples are provided in the Table 2. The PA after 360 min of UV irradiation of nano-ZnS/K before calcination (PA_{U360}) are also shown for a more precise comparison. It can be noticed that all H synthesized samples already had PA 49–62 % after 120 min. Only two M synthesized

Table 2

The PA values after 360 min of UV irradiation for nano-ZnS/K before calcination (PA_{U360}). The PA values after 120 and 360 min of UV irradiation (PA_{120} and PA_{360}), direct band gap energy (E_g), and sizes of ZnS crystallites (L_C) for the calcined nano-ZnS/K. Reaction rate constant (k_{AO7}), square of the correlation coefficient (R^2), and half-life time ($\tau_{1/2}$) values are also listed.

Row	Sample	PA_{U360} (%)	PA_{120} (%)	PA_{360} (%)	E_g (eV)	L_C (nm)	k_{AO7} (min^{-1})	R^2 (-)	$\tau_{1/2}$ (min)
	photolysis	–	2	4	–	–	–	–	–
	K	–	–	10	–	–	–	–	–
1	1H90	66	49	88	3.34	4.51	0.006	0.989	110
2	1.5H90	73	58	86	3.31	5.49	0.006	0.982	126
3	2H90	78	59	91	3.50	5.46	0.007	0.998	100
4	1H150	73	59	88	3.34	4.42	0.006	0.984	119
5	1.5H150	79	62	94	3.30	5.75	0.008	0.996	89
6	2H150	79	57	89	3.39	4.91	0.006	0.997	112
7	1H210	62	49	98	3.51	5.00	0.010	0.974	67
8	1.5H210	74	61	96	3.46	4.72	0.009	0.987	77
9	2H210	80	56	93	3.44	4.90	0.008	0.998	90
10	1M10	67	50	80	3.39	6.24	0.004	0.990	161
11	1.5M10	73	56	86	3.40	4.67	0.006	0.992	126
12	2M10	71	21	73	3.43	4.67	0.004	0.978	182
13	1M20	60	6	58	3.38	5.42	0.002	0.890	289
14	1.5M20	68	11	58	3.36	4.96	0.002	0.923	289
15	2M20	75	16	70	3.33	5.13	0.003	0.955	204
16	1M30	74	24	90	3.45	5.54	0.006	0.936	108
17	1.5M30	67	12	76	3.44	5.67	0.004	0.923	173
18	2M30	74	13	71	3.43	4.86	0.004	0.951	193

samples (1M10 and 1.5M10) had comparable PA (50 % and 56 %). Other M samples exhibited significantly lower PA (6–24 %).

Half-life time values (Table 2) for calcined samples exhibiting PA \geq 90 % are lower than 110 min with values of 67 and 108 min for the most effective nanocomposites prepared by H and M synthesis, i.e. 1H210 (PA = 98 %) and 1M30 (PA = 90 %), respectively.

Calculated E_g values for H and M synthesized samples are in the range of 3.30–3.51 eV and 3.33–3.45 eV, respectively, i.e. lower in average than values previously reported for pure nano-ZnS (3.47–3.59 eV) (Smijová et al., 2024), ZnS nanorods (3.78 eV) and spherical ZnS nanoparticles (4.06 eV) (Mají et al., 2011). Our nano-ZnS/K has lower E_g values than pure ZnS nanoparticles (Amani-Ghadim et al., 2019; Goharshadi et al., 2013; Kočí et al., 2014; La Porta et al., 2013; Seyed Dorraji et al., 2019; Soltani et al., 2014) or ZnS nanoparticles and bulk ZnS both deposited on montmorillonite (Kočí et al., 2017; Kozák et al., 2010; Praus et al., 2013). The nano-ZnS/K with reaction time 210 min led to larger band gap energy value in average (3.47 ± 0.04 eV) comparing to 150 and 90 min (3.34 ± 0.05 and 3.38 ± 0.10 eV in average). The lower E_g values of our nano-ZnS/K samples compare to other previous reports (Kočí et al., 2014; La Porta et al., 2013; Soltani et al., 2014; Goharshadi et al., 2013) is attributed to the quantum size effect (Zhang and Yang, 2013). Average PA_{360} values (89, 90, 96 % for 90, 150, 210 min, respectively) increase with increasing reaction time, while average L_C values (5.15, 5.03 and 4.87 nm, respectively) decrease. Linear dependencies of PA_{360} on E_g can be observed for reaction times 90 and 210 min (Fig. A3a). Table 2 also shows that the use of $ZnCl_2$ in excess can compensate shorter reaction time (90 and 150 min) and improve the PA_{360} of such synthesized samples. No positive effect of molar ratio higher than 1:1 on the PA_{360} was achieved for reaction time 210 min (Table 2).

In the case of M samples with reaction times 20 and 30 min, the E_g values decrease with increasing molar ratio (Table 2). For 10 min, the opposite trend for E_g values is observed. However, average PA_{360} values (80 % and 79 %) and average E_g values (3.41 ± 0.02 and 3.44 ± 0.01 eV) are very similar for reaction times 10 and 30 min, respectively. Linear dependence of PA_{360} on E_g can be observed for reaction time 30 min (Fig. A3b). Reaction time of 20 min did not result in as high PA as other M synthesis times, but the excess of $ZnCl_2$ (i.e. the increase in molar ratio from 1:1 to 2:1) helped to increase the PA (Table 2). Although the highest PA_{360} (90 %) is exhibited by the sample 1M30, the highest PA_{120} (55 %) was found for the sample 1.5M10. This PA_{120} value

is comparable with PA_{120} values of H synthesized samples.

It should be noted that the photoactive nano-ZnS represents only part by weight of the nanocomposites (\sim 35 and \sim 45 mass% for 1H210 and 1M30 samples, respectively). Comparing the PA values of nano-ZnS/K (see Table 2) and pure nano-ZnS, as reported previously (Smijová et al., 2024), the K show a clear positive effect on PA. It prevents agglomeration of the nano-ZnS leaving a larger nano-ZnS area accessible to degraded organic substances, AO7 in these cases. While the average PA_{360} for H synthesized a M synthesized nano-ZnS/K are 92 % and 74 %, respectively, 87 % and 72 % has been found for H synthesized and M synthesized nano-ZnS (Smijová et al., 2024).

Since outdoor applications of the nanocomposites are expected, it is necessary to compare the PA under UV irradiation and SL (Fig. 4). For economic reasons in practical use (especially an energy saving), uncalcined samples (2H210U and 2M20U) with the highest PA_{U360} (80 % and 75 %, respectively) were chosen for the test under SL. Photolysis under SL was also performed (Fig. 4). Due to the ability of K to absorb small amount of AO7 (see also Fig. 3), the comparison with pure K without nano-ZnS is presented in Fig. 4. For both UV irradiation and SL, the PA was determined within the same time interval (0–360 min). Since further increase in PA was detected for the M sample under SL, PA of both H and M samples was determined also after a longer time (540 min; see Fig. 4). The $\tau_{1/2}$ value for the uncalcined samples 2H210U_SL and 2M20U_SL is 98 and 147 min, respectively. The one and a half times higher $\tau_{1/2}$ value of the 2M20U_SL compared to the 2H210U_SL is acceptable considering the more than ten times faster preparation time using M synthesis (20 min vs. 210 min for the H synthesis).

Photolysis of AO7 under UV irradiation or SL was very slow. After 360 min, PA = 4 % was found both for the UV irradiation and SL. Photolysis under SL after 540 min led to only negligible increase ($PA_{540} = 5$ %). In the case of pure K without nano-ZnS, $PA_{360} = 10$ % and $PA_{540} = 13$ % was reached under UV irradiation and SL, respectively (Fig. 4). Zyouf et al. (2019) described increased photodegradation efficiency by adding kaolin to ZnO particles due to adsorption, but considering PA result of K, adsorption has a low contribution to the resulting PA. Although the lower PA was observed over time for the 2M20U compared to 2H210U, both samples reached PA $>$ 90 % after 540 min of SL irradiation. Taking into account the previous study, PA of 97 % and 92 % (H and M synthesis) were achieved after 540 min for nano-ZnS without K (Zyouf et al., 2019). In this study, comparable PA values, 97 % and 93 % for H and M synthesized nano-ZnS/K, respectively, were observed. In

Fig. 4. Dependence of PA on time for uncalcined 2H210 and 2M20 samples under UV irradiation ($\lambda = 365$ nm) or SL. For the amount of carbon in solution after PA experiments, see Table A3.

comparison with other study dealing with PA of nano-structured ZnS under SL (Aulakh et al., 2022; Jabeen et al., 2017), we have prepared comparably photoactive material, while using of photocatalyst in smaller quantities (35 and 45 mass% for 1H210 and 1M30, respectively).

The PA value of 2H210U and 2M20U samples after 120 min of SL were 48 % and 21 %, respectively. In H synthesis we obtained more photoactive sample compared to nano-ZnS sample with average hydrodynamic size 817 nm tested on Crystal violet (PA = 37 %, SL ~ 782 W/m²) (Aulakh et al., 2022). The PA of our 2H210U sample is slightly lower (48 %) after 120 min under SL compared to PA (50 %) of nano-ZnS ($L_C = 8.87$ nm) tested on Alizarin red S (Jabeen et al., 2017). The advantage of our samples is the similarity of PA under UV irradiation and SL. For 2M20U and 2H210U sample, low decrease (6 %) and increase (6 %), respectively, was observed under SL compared to UV irradiation. This difference between PA is smaller compared to the difference between PA under UV irradiation and SL after 120 min (25 %), as reported earlier for nano-ZnS ($L_C = \sim 13$ nm) (Mahvelati-Shamsabadi and Goharshadi, 2017).

3.3. Morphology of the most photoactive nanocomposites

SEM images (Fig. 5) of the most photoactive H and M synthesized samples show the nanostructured ZnS growing on the surface and edges of K (see large flat microparticles with straight edges in Figs. 5a,b). Morphologies of both samples are quite similar. SEM analysis revealed that both preparation methods lead to the round shaped nano-ZnS particles having sizes in range of 10–306 nm (1H210) and 15–432 nm (1M30), only partially agglomerated on the K surface. Elements mapping using EDX analysis (Figs. 5c,d) showed an uneven distribution of the nano-ZnS. This is consistent with the observation (Fig. 5a,b) that some K particles are completely covered by ZnS agglomerates, while others have only a small amount of nano-ZnS. The almost identical distribution of Zn and S (see the similarity of patterns in Zn and O maps) in each sample proves the presence of ZnS and no ZnO (see no similar patterns in Zn and O maps). The absence of ZnO agrees well with XRPD analysis (Fig. 1). Potential oxidation of ZnS to ZnO was not detected.

3.4. Toxicity of nanocomposites

Lipid peroxidation tests were performed on nano-ZnS/K samples and

Fig. 5. Detailed SEM images of a) 1H210 and b) 1M30, the most photoactive samples for each preparation method. EDX maps of the distribution of Zn, S, Al, Si, and O from SEM images with smaller scale, c) 1H210 and d) 1M30, are also shown.

positive (TiO_2 , 21 nm) control samples (Fig. 6). Negative (blank) control was also included (Fig. 6). The absorbance of positive control significantly exceeds the absorbance corresponding to nano-ZnS/K samples and negative control (Fig. 6). Level of autoxidative processes in negative control even slightly exceeds peroxidation of the nano-ZnS/K samples. With respect to the positive control (absorbance 0.36 = 100 %) and negative control (absorbance 0.17 = 47 %) of the malondialdehyde (MDA) production, H and M samples inhibit (in average) the lipid peroxidation by 8 % and 11 % compared to the negative control. Pure K exhibit 5 % higher production of MDA (52 %) compared to negative control. However, considering the relative deviation of 5 %, the increase MDA is not significant. The inhibition of oxidative stress (which is related to MDA production) observed for nano-ZnS/K samples may be partially caused by reverse Fenton reaction, where the hydroxyl radicals react with ferric ions present in small amounts in K (0.56 mass% Fe_2O_3 (Janíková et al., 2017)). There are several studies similarly describing the positive effect of K on the reduction of MDA formation in olive (Azizifar et al., 2022), grapevines (Bernardo et al., 2017; Bernardo et al., 2021), berries (Dinis et al., 2016), hazelnuts (Khavari et al., 2021), wheat plants (Abdallah et al., 2019), or tomatoes (Cantore et al., 2009). Drought stress, i.e. summer stress impact, is associated with the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and subsequent increase in the amount of MDA in plants leading to their degradation (Abdallah et al., 2019; Azizifar et al., 2022; Bernardo et al., 2021; Cantore et al., 2009; Dinis et al., 2016; Khavari et al., 2021). Foliar application of K aqueous solution improved the antioxidant capacity in berries, which was correlated with decreased production of ROS (Dinis et al., 2016). In olives and tomatoes, significant reduction of MDA accumulation associated with enhanced yield was observed after K foliar application (Abdallah et al., 2019; Azizifar et al., 2022; Cantore et al., 2009). Moreover, K foliar application on wheat plants led to higher nutritional value and macronutrient content (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium) (Abdallah et al., 2019). After testing on animal cells, Kawanishi et al. (2020) concluded that K submicron particles (0.2 μm) induce more ROS than the K micro-particles (4.8 μm). Considering this knowledge, the use of K particles an order of magnitude higher ($\sim 40 \mu\text{m}$) contribute to the harmlessness of nano-ZnS/K composite. MDA production could also be affected by particle size (see 3.3. section), as it was proven that the exposure of plants to particles with average size of 50 nm did not leave to any stress response (Song et al., 2019).

4. Conclusions

Kaolin KKAF (kaolinite with muscovite and quartz admixtures) was successfully applied as a matrix of nano-ZnS (sphalerite phase) in conventional hydrothermal and microwave assisted hydrothermal syntheses of nano-ZnS/K nanocomposites. SEM analysis showing kaolin particles covered with nano-ZnS on the basal surface as well as on the edges confirmed the suitability of the kaolin KKAF as a matrix

preventing agglomeration of nano-ZnS. Tests of PA using AO7 dye under UV irradiation ($\sim 365 \text{ nm}$) revealed the highest value (PA = 98 %) for H synthesized sample with reaction time 210 min and molar ratio 1:1. Achieving PA < 90 % was also possible using shorter reaction times (150 and 90 min), but with higher molar ratios $n_{\text{Zn}}:n_{\text{S}}$ (1.5:1 and 2:1). M synthesized sample with reaction time 30 min and molar ratio 1:1 had the PA = 90 %. In M synthesis, the excess of Zn^{2+} precursor did not have clear positive effect on PA. Compared to previous studies, the prepared nano-ZnS/K composites exhibit lower E_g values. This is one of the important results indicating potential for outdoor applications. PA evaluated under direct sunlight after 540 min was 97 % and 93 % for H and M synthesized nano-ZnS/K samples, respectively. The H and M samples inhibit the lipid peroxidation by 8 % and 11 % (in average) compared to the negative (blank) control. The nano-ZnS/K samples also show lower MDA production compared to pure K sample. The non-toxicity and high PA under natural sunlight suggest the potential for outdoor use of nano-ZnS/K nanocomposites. e.g. water purification or addition to building materials. For the practical degradation of pollutants in water, the anchoring of nano-ZnS on K having micrometric dimensions is advantageous due to the sedimentation of the nano-ZnS/K and thus the easier removal of the used nano-ZnS/K from the purified water. Sedimentation of nanoparticles is extremely slow, several mm per 24 h (Markus et al., 2015) and therefore unsuitable for practice. The addition of nano-ZnS/K to building materials could increase their strength (Wu et al., 2022) and lead to self-cleaning ability as reported in the case of a similar material nano- TiO_2/K (Matějka et al., 2008; Morjène et al., 2021).

Future research will focus on further toxicity testing as well as evaluating the effectiveness of nano-ZnS/K nanocomposites in the mentioned practical applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Julie Smijová: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Jonáš Tokarský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Kateřina Mamulová Kutlákova:** Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Pavlına Peikertová:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Roman Gabor:** Validation, Investigation. **Jirı́ Pavlovský:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Hana Rajhelová:** Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

Fig. 6. Lipid peroxidation test results of the nano-ZnS/K samples prepared by (a) H synthesis and (b) M synthesis. Results for negative blank control (N), positive control (TiO_2 , 21 nm) and pure kaolinite (K) are also displayed.

the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data for Rapid microwave-assisted hydrothermal in situ synthesis of nano-ZnS/kaolinite nanocomposite: a non-toxic photocatalyst active under UV and sunlight (Original data) (ZENODO)

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2024.107669>.

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